

Uncovering pre-European contact leprosy in the Americas and its enduring persistence

Abstract:

Leprosy, primarily caused by *Mycobacterium leprae*, is considered a disease introduced to the Americas during European colonization. However, the recent discovery of a second leprosy agent, *M. lepromatosis*, mainly found in the Americas, challenges this view. Here, we show that *M. lepromatosis* infected humans in the Americas before European contact. By screening 389 ancient and 408 contemporary samples, we nearly tripled available genetic data of the species. Phylogenetic analyses revealed distinct human-infecting clades, with one dominating North America since colonial times. The presence of millennia-old strains in North and South America suggests a widespread distribution of *M. lepromatosis* during the Late Holocene, demonstrating a long-standing history of *M. lepromatosis*-borne leprosy in the Americas before European arrival.

One-Sentence Summary: Leprosy caused by *M. lepromatosis* infected humans in the Americas for millennia.

Main Text

Infectious diseases have greatly influenced and shaped the history of the Americas during the European conquest (1–5). During this fateful process, a whole range of pathogens, documented in historical records or currently prevalent in the region, have been introduced from other parts of the world (5–9). However, the infectious diseases that existed in the continent prior to the European invasion and their influence on contemporary epidemiological landscapes is far less understood, and has been inferred from four main sources: *i*) endemism and heightened prevalence within the continent related to others (e.g., Chagas disease (10)), *ii*) paleopathological evidence in skeletal remains (11–13), *iii*) phylogenomic analyses of extant pathogen strains indicating a putative origin in the Americas (e.g., treponemal diseases such as endemic syphilis) (14), and *iv*) ancient DNA (aDNA) approaches (e.g., hepatitis B (15), treponemal diseases (*Treponema pallidum*) (16) and tuberculosis caused by *Mycobacterium pinnipedii* (2, 17)).

Leprosy, one of the oldest (18) and most stigmatizing diseases in human history (19–21), is considered an infectious disease introduced to the Americas during European colonization (22, 23). This introduction was associated with *Mycobacterium leprae*, the most widespread leprosy-causing bacterium worldwide (24–27), which continues to be also the main cause of leprosy in the Americas. More recently, in 2008, a second leprosy-causing species, *Mycobacterium lepromatosis*, was identified (28); this species has been reported almost exclusively in the Americas, primarily in Mexico, with additional cases in the USA, Canada, Brazil and the Caribbean (29–32). Very few cases have been reported in other continents, with only two cases in Singapore (33), two cases in Myanmar (31), and a few in red squirrels from Great Britain and Ireland (34) (table S1). *M. leprae* and *M. lepromatosis* are uncultivable *in vitro*, and their differential diagnosis can only be made through

Uncovering pre-European contact leprosy in the Americas and its enduring persistence

Simplified text for a wide non-scientific audience

Abstract:

Leprosy is a disease that has long been linked to a bacterium called *Mycobacterium leprae*, which arrived in the Americas with European colonizers. But scientists recently discovered a second bacterium, *Mycobacterium lepromatosis*, that also causes leprosy and is mostly found in the Americas. This suggests leprosy may have existed in the Americas even before Europeans came. In our study, we analyzed nearly 800 samples, both ancient (from Indigenous Ancestors) and modern (from people with leprosy today), and found clear evidence of *M. lepromatosis* in the Americas more than a thousand years ago. Our genetic analysis shows that this bacterium has been spreading and evolving in the region for a very long time.

One-Sentence Summary: Leprosy caused by *M. lepromatosis* infected humans in the Americas for millennia.

Main Text

Diseases brought by Europeans had a major impact on Indigenous communities in the Americas, and many of these are well documented. But the diseases that were already present in the Americas before this time are still not well understood. This study helps fill that gap by looking for ancient pathogens—microorganisms that cause disease—in very old human remains and also in samples from present-day people in the continent.

Leprosy is one of the oldest and most socially stigmatized diseases known. Historically, scientists believed it arrived in the Americas with European colonizers, when a bacterium called *Mycobacterium leprae* was introduced in the continent. This species is still the main cause of leprosy in the Americas today. However, in 2008, researchers discovered a second species that causes leprosy, called *Mycobacterium lepromatosis*. Unlike *M. leprae*, this species has been found almost exclusively in the Americas—especially in Mexico—with a few cases in the U.S., Canada, Brazil, and the Caribbean. Only a handful of cases have been reported elsewhere in the world, including in red squirrels in the UK and Ireland. Scientists cannot grow either of these bacteria in the lab, so they must use advanced DNA-based techniques to detect and study them. Until now, researchers had only sequenced the DNA of *M. lepromatosis* from three human samples (all from people of Mexican origin) and

molecular analyses (35, 36). To date, the only genomic data available from *M. lepromatosis* was obtained from three human samples from patients of Mexican origin (24, 34, 37, 38) and seven red squirrels from Great Britain/Ireland (39), thereby limiting current understanding of the genetic diversity and history of the species. Although the higher prevalence of *M. lepromatosis* in the Americas suggests a plausible emergence of the species on this continent (24), current phylogenomic data do not preclude its potential introduction from other continents (31, 33).

seven red squirrels. This very limited information makes it difficult to understand the full history and variation of this species. Although it seems likely that *M. lepromatosis* first appeared in the Americas, the available data doesn't rule out the possibility that it came from elsewhere.

A

B

Fig. 1. Contemporary and ancient sample sites in the Americas and

Figure 1. Locations of ancient and modern samples, and comparison of bacterial genomes.

charts indicate the site location or countries from where samples were collected for screening. Charts are color-coded according to the presence or absence of *M. lepromatosis* and if they are from present-day biopsies or ancient archaeological origin. (B) Illustration of mauve progressive alignments showing possible genome rearrangements and syntenic blocks between four leprosy-causing bacterial genomes using pyGenomeViz (48). Species (and strains in parentheses) are indicated in bold on the left. Genome sizes are shown in megabases (Mb) below each genome. The Viridis color palette (Matplotlib) is used to represent genome position along the *M. lepromatosis* reference genome (NHDP-LPM-385), with a continuous gradient from start to end. Genomes that are fully syntenic with the reference—such as other *M. lepromatosis* strains—display an almost identical color order, reflecting preserved genomic structure. In contrast, the *M. leprae* TN genome shows a disrupted color sequence due to differences in genome organization relative to the coordinates of the *M. lepromatosis* reference. Gray lines connect collinear regions, while orange highlights indicate inverted blocks (on the minus strand) relative to the NHDP-LPM-385 reference.

(A) This map shows where the ancient and modern samples used in this study were found. Pie charts show whether each site had samples positive for *M. lepromatosis*, and whether the samples came from modern patients or ancient archaeological remains. (B) This image compares the DNA of four bacteria that cause leprosy. The colored bands represent how similar their genetic structure is. Strains of the same species (*M. lepromatosis*) show very similar color patterns, meaning their DNA is arranged in the same way. One strain of *M. leprae*, however, shows a very different color pattern, indicating that its genome is organized differently. The orange marks highlight segments of DNA that are flipped in direction. This helps researchers understand how these bacteria have evolved and changed over time.

Tree branch / strain	Source	Country / Region	Date	Coverage mean (X)	Breadth of coverage (%)	SNPs (counts)
NHDP-LPM-9(†) NHDP-LPM-6	This study	USA	Contemporary	59	97	4111
Red squirrels (7 strains)	Avanzi et al. 2016	British Isles	Contemporary	m: 16 – Av: 59 – M: 126	m: 97 – M: 99	m: 423 – Av: 471 – M: 514
XVII-B-357	This study	Canada	1310 Cal BP	32	98	422
AR0353	This study	Argentina	942 Cal BP	0.67	27	635
AR0018	This study	Argentina	861 Cal BP	92	99	388
PDDC (24 strains) (†)	Mostly this study	North/Central America	Contemporary	m: 0.53 – Av: 44 – M: 171	m: 15 – Av: 85 – M: 99	m: 57 – Av: 80 – M: 171

Table 1. Summary statistics of human and wild animals infecting strains included in this study. Tree branches with several strains (second and last row) and the minimum (m), average (Av) and maximum (M) values are indicated. (†) Only high-quality genomes were considered for the three shown stats of the NHDP-LPM-9/6 and the PDDC (p) clades. See table S2 for extended summary statistics.

This table summarizes key genetic information from the strains of *M. lepromatosis* found in both humans and wild animals that were analyzed in this study. For groups of strains that form specific branches in the family tree, it shows the minimum, average, and maximum values of certain genetic measures. These values help compare how similar or different the strains are within each group. Only high-quality genome data were used to calculate these numbers for two important groups: the NHDP-LPM-9/6 clade and the PDDC clade. A more detailed version of this table is available in the supplementary materials.

To investigate the contemporary distribution and diversity of *M. lepromatosis*, we screened for the presence of its DNA in an extensive collection of 408 samples, mostly collected from recent leprosy patients, from five American countries (USA, Mexico, French Guiana, Brazil, and Paraguay), which were selected based on their geographic relevance and the availability of samples. Our quantitative PCR (qPCR) assay (see materials and methods section 2.5, supplementary text note 3, Data table S1) revealed a total of 34 positive cases (Fig. 1A, Data table S1). Surprisingly, only one of the 360 samples tested in South America proved positive (Data table S1), despite previous reports of *M. lepromatosis* in South America (29, 31, 40). From these positive cases, genomic data was successfully obtained from 23 samples, by combining high-throughput short-read sequencing and targeted enrichment

To understand where *M. lepromatosis* is found today and how genetically diverse it is, the researchers tested 408 medical samples from people in five countries across the Americas: the U.S., Mexico, French Guiana, Brazil, and Paraguay. These samples mostly came from people with leprosy or symptoms that suggested leprosy. The team used a laboratory technique called quantitative PCR (or qPCR), which can detect very small amounts of DNA from a specific organism. They found 34 samples that tested positive for *M. lepromatosis*. Surprisingly, only one of these positive samples came from South America, even though past studies had reported the presence of the bacterium there. From the 34 positive cases, the researchers were able to retrieve usable DNA data from 23 of them. They used advanced techniques that combine fast DNA sequencing and targeted “fishing” for the bacterium’s

strategies (Table 1, table S2), thereby significantly increasing available data from human-infecting strains.

Due to the unculturable nature of the species, it is challenging to obtain high-quality and pure DNA directly from biopsies. For this reason, the current reference genome of *M. lepromatosis* (FJ924) was obtained through multiple re-assembly cycles of short-read data initially matched to the *M. leprae* genome, and gap filling by PCR and Sanger sequencing (37, 38). We overcome these limitations by generating high-quality long-size *M. lepromatosis* DNA from mouse footpad samples inoculated with the strain NHDP-LPM-385, isolated from a human sample from Costa Rica (29). Using a combination of long Nanopore and short Illumina reads, the NHDP-LPM-385 genome was *de novo* assembled into a single contig of 3,259,657 base pairs (bp) at median depth of 133x (table S3), and an average nucleotide identity (ANI) of 99.80% with the FJ924 genome (38) (fig. S3). Interestingly, the synteny map of *M. lepromatosis* NHDP-LPM-385 and *M. leprae* TN genomes (41), revealed a large number of genome rearrangements, including 19 inverted repeats (Fig. 1B, supplementary text note 4). This finding generally aligns with the recent analysis of the FJ924 genome (38), which identified 24 syntenic breaks and 18 inversion events relative to the TN genome. However, our analyses also revealed previously overlooked synteny changes (see figs. S1 and S2, tables S3, S4, S5, and S6, and supplementary text note 4).

Because the new NHDP-LPM-385 genome was assembled in a single contig thanks to the use of long reads, and the sequence further polished by short-reads mapping at high-coverage, we consider its resolution to be more accurate than the current FJ924 genome, and therefore we used it as a reference for genotyping and phylogenetic reconstruction (Fig. 2). Maximum likelihood phylogenetic reconstruction revealed that all but two of the present-day human-infecting strains (24 out of 26), belonged to a single, almost clonal Present-Day Dominant phylogenetic Clade (PDDC) (Fig. 2A, fig. S4, table S2). The topology of the tree was robust to the choice of genome reference or subsets of genes (figs. S5 and S6), with only minor inconsistencies observed within the PDDC due to the very low number of differential single nucleotide variants (SNVs). Strikingly, one human-infecting strain (NHDP-LPM-9) was found to be basal to all other animal and human strains (Fig. 2, fig. S4), exhibiting 4,111 SNVs relative to NHDP-LPM-385 (Data table S2), which suggests the existence of a previously unrecognized *M. lepromatosis* clade infecting humans today.

genetic material, which helped them greatly expand the number of known genomes from *M. lepromatosis* strains that infect humans.

Because *M. lepromatosis* cannot be grown in a lab, it's difficult to get clean, high-quality DNA directly from infected human tissue. The first reference genome (named FJ924) was assembled using bits of DNA that had originally been matched to *M. leprae*, the other leprosy-causing bacterium. To improve on this, the researchers grew the bacteria in the footpads of mice (a technically challenging technique), using a strain called NHDP-LPM-385 that was originally taken from a human patient in Costa Rica. They then used two DNA sequencing technologies—Nanopore for long stretches of DNA and Illumina for accurate short reads—to build a complete genome in a single piece (a “contig”) with very high coverage, meaning they had many overlapping DNA sequences (or reads) from each part of the genome to ensure accuracy. The new genome was 3.26 million DNA letters long and 99.8% identical to the older reference. When they compared the structure of this genome to that of *M. leprae*, they found many rearrangements—sections of DNA that were flipped or moved—which are called “synteny changes.” Some of these changes were known from previous studies, but the new high-quality assembly allowed the researchers to detect several that had not been seen before.

The new genome of *M. lepromatosis* (NHDP-LPM-385) was built as a single continuous piece, using long DNA reads and then refined with short, high-quality sequences or reads. This makes it more accurate than the older reference genome (FJ924), so the researchers used it as a standard for comparing all the other strains. When they built a family tree (called a phylogenetic tree) to understand the relationships between the strains, they found that 24 out of 26 modern strains from human patients belonged to one very closely related group, which they called the Present-Day Dominant Clade (PDDC). The tree was very stable, no matter which genes or references were used to build it, showing that the result is reliable. However, one particular strain (called NHDP-LPM-9) stood out: it didn't belong to this dominant group and appeared much more different, with over 4,000 genetic differences (called single nucleotide variants or SNVs). This suggests that it represents a completely new and previously unknown lineage of *M. lepromatosis* that still infects people today.

Fig. 2. Maximum likelihood (ML) phylogeny of *M. lepromatosis* strains. (A) ML tree including all 36 *M. lepromatosis* strains with available genomic data (26 newly sequenced, 10 previously published),

Figure 2. Family tree of *M. lepromatosis* strains based on their genomic DNA. (A) This image shows the evolutionary relationships between all known *M. lepromatosis* genomes (both new and previously published). On

shown both as a cladogram ignoring branch lengths (left) and as a branch-length-scaled tree (right). Tip labels are color-coded by country of origin (map inset), and host types are indicated with icons (ancient humans, present-day humans, red squirrels). Branches in red correspond to low-coverage genomes, which in some cases display artificially long branches due to spurious SNV calls from insufficient read support. The cladogram facilitates visualization of phylogenetic relationships and node support (proportion of bootstrap replicates supporting a node shown when >0.7). (B) ML tree including only high-coverage strains ($n=24$), displayed unrooted to improve resolution of clade structure. Five well-supported clades are evident (bootstrap support >0.7 indicated by red dots), each separated by >100 SNPs from their respective ancestral nodes. Within the PDDC and red squirrel clades, short terminal branches reflect recent diversification (insets magnify their internal topologies). The long branch leading to NHDP-LPM-9 was scaled down 20-fold for visualization. Branch lengths represent SNP counts, derived by multiplying RAxML branch lengths by the alignment length and scale bars are provided above each panel.

To confirm that the strain was indeed *M. lepromatosis*, we performed a phylogenetic analysis including publicly available ancient and contemporary *M. leprae* strains and involving 1,311 orthologous genes shared between both species (fig. S7, see materials and methods section 3.19, supplementary text note 6, Data table S3). The results positioned NHDP-LPM-9 as a basal *M. lepromatosis* strain that is very distantly separated from *M. leprae* (fig. S7). The basal positioning of NHDP-LPM-9 was also supported by marginal likelihood and log Bayes factor analyses, supporting this branch as the most basal outgroup in relation to other lineages in the tree (table S7, supplementary material section 3.18). The basal branch was also supported by a second strain, NHDP-LPM-6, which, despite its limited coverage (depth-of-coverage=0.2x, breadth-of-coverage= 11%), was confidently placed within this clade (Fig. 2A, Table 1, table S2, fig. S4), with numerous substitutions shared exclusively by both strains (figs. S8 and S9). The NHDP-LPM-9 genome was, however, found to have accumulated a large number of singleton SNVs, leading to a very long branch in the tree (Fig. 2B). Statistical tests and Bayesian inference suggest a particularly high evolutionary rate for NHDP-LPM-9, suggesting that this could be a hypermutating strain (supplementary text, figs. S10 and S11). These results remained consistent even after applying stringent filters to remove potential spurious variants arising from contaminant sequences or introduced during sample processing (supplementary material section 3.9, table S2, fig. S12). Hypermutating *M. leprae* strains were previously described in leprosy patients and have been attributed to deleterious mutations in DNA repair genes (*nth*, endonuclease III), favoring the emergence of drug resistance (22). Accordingly, several missense mutations were also found in NHDP-LPM-9 genes encoding DNA repair proteins such as the transcription-repair coupling factor Mfd, which could potentially explain the hypermutator genotype (table S8, supplementary text). However, none of the four genes that are known drug-resistant associated targets in *M. leprae* (22) carried mutations in NHDP-LPM-9, which rules out that this potential hypermutator genotype could have favored the occurrence of drug resistance mutations (table S9, supplementary text note 7). Importantly, the discovery of the basal NHDP-LPM-9/NHDP-LPM-6 strains reveals that there are at least two independent lineages of *M. lepromatosis* infecting humans today in North America.

To clarify the history and past prevalence of *M. lepromatosis* in the Americas, we screened a collection of 389 aDNA datasets from pre-European contact Ancestors from the

the left is a simplified version of the tree, where all branches are the same length to clearly show the structure. On the right, the branches are scaled to show how genetically different the strains are (the length of a branch is proportional to the number of mutations accumulated in that branch). The colors and icons next to the names show where each strain came from (country) and who it infected (ancient or modern human, or red squirrel). Some branches are shown in red because they are based on low-quality data and may appear longer than they really are. (B) This is a more detailed tree that includes only the 24 highest-quality genomes. It shows five main groups (called clades), which are very distinct from each other. Some groups, like those from red squirrels and many present-day human cases (PDDC), are closely related and have only recently changed, shown by short final branches. The tree also shows one unusual strain (NHDP-LPM-9) that has accumulated a significantly higher number of mutations than the others—it is so different that its branch had to be shortened to fit in the image.

To make sure that the unusual strain NHDP-LPM-9 really was *M. lepromatosis*, the researchers compared it to many ancient and modern genomes of *M. leprae* and *M. lepromatosis*, focusing on over 1,300 genes that both species share. This confirmed that NHDP-LPM-9 is clearly part of *M. lepromatosis*, but it has accumulated more differences compared to the other known strains with each other. In the phylogenetic tree, it appears at the base of the *M. lepromatosis* branch—meaning it split off very early from the rest. Another strain, NHDP-LPM-6, also grouped with it, supporting the idea that this is a separate and ancient lineage. Interestingly, NHDP-LPM-9 had an unusually large number of unique genetic changes (called singleton SNVs), which made its branch in the tree much longer than the others. This suggests it might be a “hypermutator,” meaning it accumulates mutations faster than usual, possibly due to defects in its DNA repair system. The researchers did find mutations in some of its DNA repair genes, but not in the genes linked to antibiotic resistance, so this hypermutation doesn’t seem to make the strain drug-resistant. Overall, these results show that at least two very different lineages of *M. lepromatosis* are still infecting people in North America today.

To understand how common *M. lepromatosis* was in the past, the researchers analyzed 389 ancient DNA samples (aDNA) from human remains that predate the arrival of Europeans in the

Americas, newly generated or publicly available (see materials and methods). This aDNA work involved various community engagement actions, described in detail in the Materials and Methods section 1.1. Interestingly, one Ancestor from the current territory of Canada in North America (XVII-B-357) (42), and two Ancestors (AR0018 and AR0353) in the Southern Cone of the continent returned positive identification for *M. lepromatosis*, and negative for *M. leprae* (Fig. 1A, Fig. 2A, table S10, see materials and methods section 1.3). While the XVII-B-357 maxillae exhibited slight pathological changes consistent but not specific to early leprosy stages (supplementary text, note 1), no pathological signals were macroscopically apparent on the skeletons of both other individuals. This last finding is expected as skeletal pathology only occurs in a small fraction of the population (43). The remains of the three Ancestors were radiocarbon-dated to pre-European contact times, within a relatively short time frame during the Late Holocene, around one thousand years ago (XVII-B-357: 1310 calBP, AR0018: 860 calBP and AR0353: 942 calBP, fig. S13). Consistent with the radiocarbon dates, the genomes of all three Ancestors comprised only genetic ancestry that is Indigenous to the Americas (supplementary text note 11, fig. S14, table S11).

Using a combination of high-depth sequencing and targeted enrichment (the latter was not necessary for XVII-B-357), we obtained highly covered *M. lepromatosis* genomes from XVII-B-357 (31X) and AR0018 (92X). DNA damage patterns were consistent with previous reports for ancient mycobacterial genomes (2, 23) (figs. S15, S16 and S17, table S14, and supplementary text note 8). Remarkably, despite their extremely distant locations, both ancient strains cluster next to each other and basal to the PDDC from North and Central America, with XVII-B-357 diverging first (Fig. 2B). However, the two branches are well separated and relatively long, forming what seemingly represent distinct clades, suggesting each has undergone a long independent history. Although the genome of AR0353 had low coverage (depth-of-coverage=0.67X and breadth-of-coverage=27%), it consistently grouped with AR0018 in all of our multiple phylogenetic tests (including those shown in Fig. 2A, fig. S4), further supporting the existence of a distinct clade in South America.

Our results combining ancient and present-day DNA data revealed five distinct clades of *M. lepromatosis*, identified by the following strains: (i) the most basal, represented by the NHDP-LPM-9 and NHDP-LPM-6 strains, (ii) the red squirrel-infecting strains, (iii) the ancient XVII-B-357 strain, (iv) the AR0018/AR0353 strains, and (v) the 24 PDDC strains (Fig. 2B). The phylogenetic tree shows that each clade is clearly differentiated by multiple SNVs, with the nodes defining them being well-supported. Additionally, the branches extending from these nodes to the sampled strains are relatively long, indicating a substantial evolutionary history of unsampled diversity since the initial divergence of each clade. However, within the red squirrel and PDDC clades, the sampled strains exhibit very short terminal branches from their most recent common node, suggesting that while these clades experienced prolonged periods of divergence from their respective ancestors, the extant strains within them have

Americas. These samples came from previous studies or were newly collected, and the research was done with consent of Indigenous communities. They found three individuals who were clearly infected with *M. lepromatosis*: one from what is now Canada (named XVII-B-357) and two from Argentina (AR0018 and AR0353). None of them had DNA from *M. leprae*, the other leprosy bacterium. One of the skeletons (XVII-B-357) showed some mild signs in the jawbone that could be linked to early leprosy, but these signs were not conclusive. The other two skeletons didn't show visible bone changes, which is not surprising because most people with leprosy do not develop changes that affect the skeleton. Radiocarbon dating showed that all three individuals lived about 1,000 years ago, well before European colonization. Genetic analysis also confirmed that these individuals had ancestry typical of Indigenous peoples of the Americas. This means that *M. lepromatosis* was already circulating among Native populations in both North and South America long before Europeans arrived.

To better understand the genetics of the ancient strains, researchers used deep DNA sequencing, which means reading a high number of DNA molecules (over 100 million DNA fragments), to ensure accuracy and high-genome coverage. For two of the individuals (XVII-B-357 from Canada and AR0018 from Argentina), they managed to recover high-quality *M. lepromatosis* genomes. The DNA damage in these samples matched what is normally seen in other ancient bacterial DNA, confirming their authenticity (i.e., that they are old). When the researchers compared these two ancient genomes, they were surprised to find that—despite the great distance between Canada and Argentina—the strains were closely related and branched off near the base of the phylogenetic tree, before the Present-Day Dominant Clade (PDDC), which includes most modern strains from Mexico and the U.S. The Canadian strain (XVII-B-357) split off first, followed by the Argentinian one (AR0018). This suggests that these two ancient strains came from different but related lineages that had already been evolving independently for a long time. Although the third ancient genome (from individual AR0353 in Argentina) had lower quality and coverage, it still grouped with AR0018 in all the genetic tests. This strengthens the evidence that there was a separate, now distinct lineage of *M. lepromatosis* in South America during pre-colonial times.

By combining ancient and modern DNA data, researchers identified five clearly distinct genetic groups—or clades—of *Mycobacterium lepromatosis*. These include:

1. The most ancient (or "basal") clade, made up of two modern strains from the U.S. (NHDP-LPM-9 and NHDP-LPM-6).
2. A clade formed by 7 strains found in red squirrels from the British Isles.
3. The ancient strain from Canada (XVII-B-357).
4. The two ancient strains from Argentina (AR0018 and AR0353).
5. A large group of very similar modern strains mostly found in Mexico and the U.S., known as the Present-Day Dominant Clade (PDDC).

These groups were identified using a phylogenetic tree, which as explained above, is like a family tree for bacteria. Each group is

only recently diverged from each other. To assess the timing of divergence between strains and clades, we conducted molecular clock analyses, including the contemporary and ancient strains of highest quality (breadth-of-coverage >95% and average depth-of-coverage >10X) (fig. S18), using a relaxed clock model best-fitting our data after thorough testing (fig. S19, see materials and methods, fig. S21, supplementary text note 9). The estimated most recent common ancestor (MRCA) of all clades, including NHDP-LPM-9, dates to a median of ~9400 BP (Fig. 3A, Internal Node 1 in fig. S20A), followed by an MRCA of median ~3200 BP for the node of the red squirrels branch, ~2200 BP for the XVII-B-357 and ~1500 BP to the node separating the AR0018/AR0353 and PDDC. In our view, the most parsimonious interpretation of these results is that the divergence of these clades occurred within the Americas, as the estimated dates fall within a period of limited contact between the Americas and other continents. They also reveal a very recent expansion of the red squirrels and PDDC clades, with strains diverging from a common node dated at a median of ~105 BP and ~280 BP, respectively, both falling within a post-European contact period.

Taking advantage of our new data, we recalculated the divergence time between *M. leprae* and *M. lepromatosis* by analyzing ancient and contemporary strains of both species. The most recent common ancestor was estimated at 720 kya using a relaxed clock model with a coalescent exponential distribution (median value, with a 95% credible interval: 660 to 792 kya, Fig. 3B). We also tested a second model, which uses as prior a different and more naïve distribution of population size ($1/X$), which estimated older dates, with a median of 2.015 Mya (95% credible interval: 1.507 Mya to 2.583 Mya, Fig. 3B). Importantly, these estimates are much more recent than the 14 Mya reported in previous work (24, 38), highlighting the value of increased sample size—achieved with new modern genomes—and greater temporal depth—through the inclusion of ancient genomes—for improving molecular clock estimates in slow-evolving pathogens. Indeed, estimates of evolutionary rates for these bacteria and others in this genus imply about one substitution every five years across the genome (0.19 subs/year for a genome of 3.2 Mbp), such that a divergence time of several million years between these two species would result in saturation of most sites in the genome. Consequently, this estimate represents a more plausible scenario considering the genomic similarities between both bacterial species (92% ANI, fig. S22) and the very similar symptomatology they produce.

defined by many unique genetic differences (called SNVs), and the longer the "branch" leading to a strain, the longer it has been evolving on its own. Interestingly, some groups like the red squirrel clade and the dominant modern clade (PDDC) have short branches between the present-day strains, suggesting that their current diversity results from a relatively recent differentiation. But the long branches connecting these groups to the rest of the tree suggest that many intermediate strains are missing or unsampled, showing gaps in our knowledge of the pathogen's history and diversification. To estimate how long ago these groups separated from one another, researchers used a method called "molecular clock analysis." This method estimates divergence dates between strains and clades by looking at how many genetic changes have accumulated over time, and assuming that mutations get accumulated at a certain measurable rate, like the tic-tac of a clock. The results suggest that all five clades started diverging from a common ancestor around 9,400 years ago. The red squirrel group split off around 3,200 years ago, the Canadian strain around 2,200 years ago, and the South American/modern group split about 1,500 years ago. The modern strains in squirrels and humans seem to have expanded quite recently, after European contact, around 100 and 280 years ago, respectively. Importantly, the estimated emergence periods of each of the five lineages of *M. lepromatosis* support the idea that they have all evolved within the Americas.

With the new genetic data available, the researchers re-estimated when *Mycobacterium leprae* and *Mycobacterium lepromatosis*—the two bacteria that cause leprosy—last shared a common ancestor. This is important to understand how long ago these two species split from one another. Using a type of genetic modeling called a "relaxed molecular clock," which estimates timing based on the number of mutations over time, they found that the most likely date of divergence was around 720,000 years ago. A second and less informative model gave an older estimate of around 2 million years ago. But the important information here is that both estimates are much more recent than the 14 million years suggested by earlier studies. Why does this matter? Because although bacteria in this group tend to mutate slowly—about one genetic change every five years, if the two species had really diverged 14 million years ago, their genomes would have become much more different than what it is seen. However, they still share about 92% of their DNA and cause very similar symptoms. That makes these newer, younger divergence estimates more reasonable and better supported by the data.

Fig. 3. Molecular clock analyses of *M. lepromatosis* and estimation of divergence time from *M. leprae*. (A) Bayesian time-calibrated phylogeny inferred from 21 *M. lepromatosis* genomes obtained from red squirrels (italicized, n=6) in Great Britain and Ireland, and from contemporary (n=13) and ancient (n=2) humans. Tree reconstruction was performed in BEAST v2.6.6 (49) using a relaxed molecular clock model. Contemporary human strains originate mainly from the USA and Mexico, while the reference genome (NHDP-LPM-385) was obtained from a patient from Costa Rica (29). Node labels indicate median divergence dates (in years before present), and colored distributions above selected nodes show posterior probability densities of node ages, estimated from 1000 posterior samples. (B) Posterior distributions of the estimated divergence times between *M. leprae* and *M. lepromatosis* using relaxed clock models with two different priors on the distributions of the population size, the one on X (1/X) and exponential, with the 1/X being

Figure 3. Estimating when *M. lepromatosis* evolved and how long ago it split from *M. leprae*. (A) This tree shows how different *M. lepromatosis* strains are from each other and estimates when they split apart. It includes DNA from 21 genomes: 6 from red squirrels in the UK and Ireland, 13 from modern human cases (mostly in the USA and Mexico), and 2 from ancient humans. The tree was built using a method called a “relaxed molecular clock,” which helps scientists estimate how long ago each split happened based on mutation rates. Colored bars show how certain the scientists are about each estimated date. (B) This graph compares two ways of estimating how long ago *M. lepromatosis* and *M. leprae* shared a common ancestor. Both methods suggest that these two bacteria split much more recently than previously thought—between 700,000 and 2 million years ago, rather than the 14 million years ago estimated in two previous publications.

the maximally uninformative prior. Despite the substantial differences in these posterior densities, both population size priors infer a much more recent divergence time than the 14 million years previously estimated (24, 38).

Previous archaeological, paleopathological, and phylogenomic work have dismissed the presence of leprosy in the Americas during pre-colonial times due to the lack of clear osteological evidence in ancient human remains from the continent (44, 45), whereas such evidence is commonly observed in archaeological remains from Europe. This was also supported by phylogenomic and ancient DNA studies showing that leprosy caused by *M. leprae* was brought to the Americas from Europe and Africa, which undoubtedly had a significant impact on Indigenous populations (22, 23, 46). While our findings do not challenge the introduction of *M. leprae*-born leprosy into the Americas by European and African populations, they reveal that *M. lepromatosis* was already circulating within human populations across the continent several centuries before the European arrival. Our results, therefore, strongly suggest that leprosy caused by *M. lepromatosis* was a long-lasting endemic disease extending at a continent-wide scale in pre-European times.

Despite our extensive screening efforts of both ancient and modern samples, the diversity of *M. lepromatosis* strains recovered in this study underscores how little is known about the pathogen's evolutionary and epidemiological history. The long branches observed between nodes and tips of each clade, with no intermediate branching strains, suggest that significant unsampled diversity exists—or existed—, leaving substantial gaps in the timeline of its evolutionary and spread trajectories. This contrasts with the phylogenetic structure observed in *M. leprae* (fig. S7B), where a broader and more extensive sampling of strains across different time periods and geographic regions reveals deeper branches and more intricate intra-lineage diversification. These findings underscore the pressing need for further sampling to resolve the transmission dynamics and historical spread of *M. lepromatosis*, not only in the Americas but also in other regions, such as Asia, where the pathogen has been reported but remains genomically uncharacterized.

Nonetheless, our data provide valuable insights and generate new hypotheses regarding the pathogen's history. The discovery of ancient strains in both North and South America confirms that *M. lepromatosis* infected humans in pre-European times and was geographically widespread across the continent. The phylogenetic reconstruction reveals at least five distinct clades, four of which are found in the Americas. The presence of a fifth clade infecting red squirrels in the British Isles raises the hypothesis that this lineage also originated in the Americas, given its estimated divergence time of 3,200 BP—well before any known historical or likely zoonotic connections between the Americas and other continents that could have facilitated transcontinental pathogen spread. Additionally, most strains recovered in this study belong to a single clade of highly similar strains (PDDC), which appears to predominate in Mexico and other regions of North America. Although this suggests a higher prevalence of the pathogen in North America today, the lack of *M. lepromatosis* in most tested South American samples may also possibly reflect gaps in current sampling efforts rather than a true absence of the pathogen in the region.

The phylogenetic structure of *M. lepromatosis* also raises intriguing questions about recent transmission events. The red

Until now, scientists believed that leprosy didn't exist in the Americas before Europeans arrived. This idea was based on two things: 1) archaeologists hadn't found clear signs of leprosy in ancient skeletons from the Americas, and 2) genetic studies showed that *M. leprae*, the better-known cause of leprosy, was brought to the Americas by Europeans and Africans after colonization. While this study agrees that *M. leprae* came with colonizers, it also shows something new: that *M. lepromatosis*—the other leprosy-causing bacteria—was already present in the Americas long before that. The discovery of ancient strains in both North and South America proves that *M. lepromatosis* had been circulating among Indigenous peoples for centuries. This suggests that a form of leprosy was already widespread across the continent, making it an endemic disease in the Americas before European contact.

Even though in this work many ancient and modern samples were studied, we still know very little about the history and spread of *M. lepromatosis*. When scientists build phylogenetic trees (which show how strains are related), the branches connecting different strains of *M. lepromatosis* are long, and there are few strains in between. This means many past strains or intermediate evolutionary stages are still missing from our data, leaving big gaps in the timeline of how this bacterium diversified and spread. This is very different from *M. leprae*, the better-known leprosy bacterium, where researchers have studied many more strains across time and geography. As a result, *M. leprae*'s tree shows much more detail about how it evolved. These results highlight how important it is to keep looking for more samples of *M. lepromatosis*, both in the Americas and in other parts of the world—especially Asia, where the bacterium has been found but not yet studied genetically.

Even with many unanswered questions, the findings of this work reveal important information and open new lines of investigation. The discovery of ancient *M. lepromatosis* strains in both North and South America confirms that the bacterium was already infecting humans across the continent long before Europeans arrived. By investigating the genetic relationships between strains, five major groups (called clades) were found, four of which are from strains collected in the Americas. Interestingly, the fifth clade was found in red squirrels in the British Isles. Since this group seems to have split off from the others about 3,200 years ago—well before any known contact between the Americas and Europe—it's most likely that this squirrel clade actually originated in the Americas. Most of the modern strains we found belong to one group that is almost genetically identical and very common in Mexico and parts of the U.S. This suggests that the bacterium is more common in North America today. However, it's also possible that we're just missing data from other regions—like South America—because we haven't sampled enough, or in the right places, there yet.

The genetic structure of *M. lepromatosis* also gives us clues about how it might have spread in more recent times. The

squirrel clade exhibits a long branch from the root node to the present-day strains, followed by extremely short terminal branches, suggesting a long period of unsampled diversity before a recent expansion. The estimated time to the most recent common ancestor (MRCA) of red squirrel strains at ~105 BP aligns with historical timelines of human-mediated animal introductions to the British Isles and the UK—such as the grey squirrels introduced in the 19th century (47)—, supporting the hypothesis of a recent spillover from an American reservoir. However, given the absence of intermediate branches, we cannot exclude the possibility that an earlier introduction occurred at any point along this long branch and from geographic regions that remain still largely unsampled, with a subsequent expansion within the UK and British Isles occurring only recently. Similarly, the estimated MRCA of the PDDC clade at ~280 BP raises the possibility that its expansion was influenced by demographic and social changes following European colonization. The early colonial period was marked by dramatic upheavals, including population displacements, ecological disruptions, and altered human-animal interactions, which could have facilitated the spread of the pathogen. However, given the limited number of strains analyzed and the absence of samples covering different historical regions and periods, this remains a hypothesis rather than a definitive conclusion. Finally, the divergence time estimates between North and South American clades suggest that *M. lepromatosis* underwent large-scale dispersal across the continent during the Late Holocene, with the MRCA between the PDDC and AR0018 estimated at ~1,500 BP, followed by the node separating the ancient XVII-B-357 strain in North America dated to ~2,200 BP. These findings suggest intercontinental movements of the pathogen over the past millennia, but due to the large time intervals separating these clades, the directionality of spread remains uncertain.

By integrating ancient and modern pathogen genomics, this study provides a critical first step in reconstructing the evolutionary history of *M. lepromatosis*. However, the long and unsampled evolutionary gaps in our phylogenetic reconstructions highlight the vast unknowns that remain. Expanding sampling efforts across different geographic regions and time periods, investigating potential non-human reservoirs, and improving epidemiological surveillance will be essential to refining our understanding of the pathogen's transmission dynamics, persistence, and historical spread. Addressing these gaps will not only clarify the origins and evolutionary trajectory of *M. lepromatosis* but also provide a broader perspective on the complex interplay between human migration, environmental factors, and zoonotic reservoirs in shaping the epidemiology of infectious diseases.

group of strains found in red squirrels in the British Isles has a long gap in its genetic history, followed by the differentiation of very closely related strains today. This pattern suggests this clade existed and diversified for a long time in an unknown place, without being sampled, and we have only sampled strains derived from a recent spreading or expansion. The estimated common ancestor of these squirrel strains dates to about 105 years ago, which fits with the historical introduction of animals like grey squirrels to the British Isles in the 1800s. This supports the idea that the disease might have been brought from the Americas with animals, and only started spreading among squirrels in the UK more recently. However, because we don't have samples from in-between time points or regions, we can't rule out the possibility that the introduction happened earlier, but remained undetected. A similar pattern is seen in the PDDC clade—the group of strains common in modern North America—whose recent common ancestor dates to around 280 years ago. This time frame overlaps with the early colonial period, which saw major disruptions, like changes in human populations, the environment, and interactions with animals. These events may have helped the disease spread. But since we only have a limited number of strains and few samples from different times and places, this remains a theory—not confirmed evidence. Finally, the estimated divergence times between strains from North and South America suggest that *M. lepromatosis* spread widely across the continent in the past few thousand years. For example, the PDDC and South American AR0018 clades share a common ancestor from about 1,500 years ago, and the North American ancient strain (XVII-B-357) separated from others about 2,200 years ago. This means the disease was likely moving across long distances in the Americas during the Late Holocene, though we still don't know the exact direction of its spread and by which means.

By studying DNA from both ancient and modern samples, this work takes an important first step in tracing the history of *M. lepromatosis*. However, many parts of that history are still missing because we don't yet have DNA from enough times and places. To fully understand how this bacteria spread and survived over time, we'll need more samples—especially from different regions, time periods, and potential animal carriers. Filling in these gaps will help reveal not just where *M. lepromatosis* came from, but also how it spread between people and possibly between humans and animals. This will also help scientists better understand how diseases in general are influenced by human movement, environmental changes, and animals that can carry infections.

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Ancient DNA data are accessible through the Owey platform hosted by Institut Pasteur (37). For data derived from Ancestor XVII-B-357 (Canada), requests must be approved by the Lax Kw'alaams and Metlakatla First Nations (contact information in Acknowledgements). For individuals from Argentina (AR0353 and AR0018), access is granted via the Owey request process; community consultation may be added at their discretion.

The code used for bioinformatic analyses and supplementary tables are available through Zenodo (38).

Disclaimer

The views expressed in this article are solely the opinions of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official policies of the U. S. Department of Health and Human Services or the Health Resources and Services Administration, nor does mention of the department or agency names imply endorsement by the U.S. Government.

Supplementary Material

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